

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in
Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation
packages

Learning stories on governance solutions

Deliverable 4.2

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon H2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement 101036683.

Deliverable Number and Name	D4.2 - Learning stories on governance solutions
Work Package	WP4 – Actionable adaptive solutions implementation
Dissemination Level	Public
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Date Due	30-09-2024
Date Submitted	30-09-2024
File Name	TransformAr_WP4_D4.2_Learning stories on governance solutions_v1_30-09-2024
Status	
Reviewed by (if applicable)	Margaretha Breil
Suggested citation	Vincent, A., Cools, J., Etzi, F., Karozis, S., Ogando-Vidal, A., Pavlidi, E., Puddu, M., Rodríguez-García, C., Sfetsos, T., Tzempelikos, D., Zarikos, G. (2024) Learning stories on governance solutions. TransformAr Deliverable 4.2, H2020 grant no. 101036683

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This document has been prepared in the framework of the European project TransformAr. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement no. 101036683.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1 Learning stories on governance solutions

The EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change empowers European regions and local authorities to achieve climate resilience by 2030. In order to accelerate action to adapt to the consequences of climate change at regional and local level, novel governance solutions are essential. The TransformAr project, in support of the EU Mission on Adaptation, has demonstrated three governance solutions for adaptation. Each solution aims to resolve multiple governance challenges.

Climate change adaptation is considered a complex issue, often referred to as a "wicked problem." This means that governments face a range of difficulties, such as shifting political priorities, power struggles, conflicting interests, resistance from key groups, and limited opportunities to make significant changes. But when a window of opportunity arises we need an innovative set of tools to overcome governance challenges and to accelerate implementation of climate adaptation projects. More specifically we need:

Practical methodologies for quantitative assessments, methods for monitoring and evaluation and for dealing with uncertainties

Better integration of knowledge in decision-making by developing scenarios and identifying solutions and priorities

Vertical policy integration, cutting across different jurisdictional levels

The involvement of non-state stakeholders and the broad public to take common decisions with policy-makers that support long term visions

Chapter's 1.1-1.3 will explore various projects, their backgrounds, and the challenges they faced in changing their environments and governance systems to achieve transformational change. Each case showcases innovative ways to tackle the difficulties of managing climate adaptation. The challenges tackled are summarized in Table 1. The solutions presented involve assessment methods that heavily involve local stakeholders. These methods help make sense of complex climate data, acknowledge uncertainties, and promote awareness and knowledge sharing.

Figure 1. Location of the project countries, demo regions and governance solutions.

Table 1 Challenges tackled by four TransformAr partners in their governance solutions

Challenges tackled

1.1 Resilience Index in Galicia (Spain): decoding climate challenges

The first governance tool is the **resilience index** in **Galicia**. This tool provides a comprehensive assessment of climate adaptation needs for the mussel aquaculture sector in Galicia. It helps decision-makers in both the productive and political sectors make informed decisions about governance and policy formulation. This collaborative, problem-solving approach not only makes complex climate data accessible to a broad range of stakeholders but also fosters collaboration among them.

1.2 Coastal Contracts in Sardinia (Italy): fostering cross-sectoral cooperation for integrated wetland management

The second tool is the **coastal contract** in **Oristano**. This governance approach enhances cross-sectoral cooperation at the local level. It aims to manage coastal wetlands more effectively by overcoming the fragmentation of local governance through collaborative decision-making and centralized climate data monitoring.

1.3 Climate innovation hub in Egaleo (Greece): a meeting space for collaboration and awareness

The third tool is the **climate innovation hub** in **Egaleo**. Unlike the "virtual" climate adaptation platforms mentioned earlier, the climate innovation hub is a physical meeting space in Egaleo, Greece. It brings data on climate and weather to the policymakers and the citizens and of Egaleo, thus supporting decision-making. By educating youth and by raising awareness Egaleo gains public support for climate adaptation actions.

1.1 Resilience index Galicia, Spain

Measuring adaptive capacity of the aquaculture value chain in Galicia

The Resilience Index (RI) combines complex **climate data**, **operational processes**, and **resilience factors** into a clear and comprehensive assessment of the value chain's adaptive capacity. This tool helps decision-makers in both the productive and political fields make informed decisions regarding governance and the formulation of new policies, strategically adapting operations to mitigate the risk of production interruptions due to the effects of climate change.

Key learnings

- **Stakeholder engagement:** Actively involving stakeholders from the outset significantly boosts project acceptance, underlining the importance of early and proactive stakeholder engagement.
- **Collaborative innovation and problem-solving:** The emphasis on interaction and collaboration among Government, Industry, Academia, Environmental organizations, and Civil Society highlights the essential role of inclusiveness, sustainability, and social responsibility in effectively addressing complex challenges and promoting sustainable development.
- **Holistic assessment:** The interconnected evaluation of risks, vulnerabilities, resilience factors, and actionable recommendations underscores the importance of a holistic approach to informed decision-making in enhancing resilience.
- **Awareness:** Engaging stakeholders has contributed to raise climate change awareness, highlighting the importance of sharing knowledge and understanding in addressing environmental challenges.

Climate and Oceanographic Threats

Galicia region faces the risk of increasingly frequent and intense winter storms, which can cause damage to coastal infrastructure and flooding. Other climatic risks include heat waves, droughts and a longer fire season. For mussel aquaculture, threats include **damage to rafts structures** and **biomass losses** due to extreme weather conditions, availability of **mussel seed**, increased harmful algal blooms, increased water temperature and stratification. These threats not only pose significant risks to the mussel aquaculture sector but also threatens the broader **socioeconomic stability of the region**. The Resilience Index (RI) aims to transform these challenges into opportunities by providing a comprehensive **tool to assist in assessing and improving the adaptive capacity of key sectors**, ensuring their sustainable development in the face of climate change.

About the region

Galicia, located in the northwest of Spain, covers just 5.8% of the country's territory but holds 32.8% of its coastline (1,659 km) due to its intricate Atlantic coast and multiple estuaries known as Rías. Galicia supplies 40% of Europe's mussels with over 3,000 rafts. The Ría de Arousa, on the southwest coast, stands out as the largest and most productive, hosting about a 70% of the Galician mussel rafts. Mussel aquaculture directly employs 3.890 people in the region.

Climate and oceanographic hazards

Heatwaves, sea level rise, extreme precipitations and storms, upwelling and acidification.

Sector

Agriculture and Fisheries

Key system

Mussel aquaculture

Resilience Index development: Addressing Adaptation Challenges in the Mussel Aquaculture

Before developing the case study, the mussel aquaculture sector in Galicia was faced with scattered data, diverse risk assessments and a scarcity of strategic guidance for adapting to climate change. This made it difficult for stakeholders to develop **cohesive and proactive strategies**. To bridge this gap, the REDE research group of the University of Vigo (UVigo), in collaboration with the Sea Technology Centre (CETMAR) and the Institute of Marine Research (IIM-CSIC), developed the Resilience Index (RI) within the TransformAr project.

The RI is a **synthetic or composite index** designed to offer a comprehensive assessment of the adaptive capacity of the value chain in response to climate change effects. Composite indexes aggregate several indicators to encapsulate the characteristics of a system, such as a value chain, especially when the concepts are not directly measurable. By linking these concepts to observable variables, known as indicators, the RI effectively **assesses the level of resilience**.

The RI formula can be represented as follows:

$$RI = \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i \cdot Dm_i$$

Where:

i represents the number of resilience dimensions analysed.

β_i denotes the weight assigned to each resilience factor i , reflecting its relative importance.

Dm_i is the score or value of the resilience dimension i .

For the identification of the resilience dimensions (Dm_i) that would take part on the formula as variables, a literature review on value chains has been conducted. The dimensions identified include **Governance, R+D+I, Risk Management, Collaboration and Operational Environment**. These dimensions have been broken down into 4 resilience factors each for a deeper assessment, making a total of 20 resilience factors.

For the calculation of the **weights and the values of the dimensions** (variables), a hybrid methodology was employed, integrating climate data, climatic scenarios, and inputs from literature review and experts & stakeholders feedback.

Figure 2. Resilience Index development process

The development of the RI formula was characterized by a robust and **collaborative engagement with stakeholders and experts** from the outset and throughout each phase of the process. This inclusive approach ensured that the index was not only scientifically rigorous but also practically applicable. As shown in Figure 2, this process was conducted through two main consultation dynamics to experts and stakeholders using the **Delphi method**¹, a structured communication technique that relied on three rounds of questioning in each consultation with the aim of achieving consensus.

The development of RI is divided into three main stages:

- **First consultation (Delphi 1):** Stakeholders and experts evaluated the level of impact of 7 key climate and ocean-meteorological variables (air temperature, water surface temperature, rainfall, sea level, upwelling, wind, and water acidification) on the 10 main mussel aquaculture processes. The output of this assessment was a set of 13 risk scenarios with potential risk to affect mussel production due to climate change out of 70 scenarios assessed.

¹ RAND Corporation (2024). Delphi Method. Retrieved from <https://www.rand.org/topics/delphi-method.html>, June 12th, 2024.

- **Second consultation (Delphi 2):** The 13 selected risk scenarios from Delphi 1 were combined with the 20 resilience factors identified through literature review to determine their level of contribution to the value chain resilience. Experts assessed how these factors could moderate the effects of specific risk scenarios on key production processes. The results were weighted based on the average scores from Delphi 1, resulting in the contribution of each resilience dimension to the adaptive capacity of mussel aquaculture, represented in the RI formula as β_i .
- **Assessment of adaptive capacities:** An evaluation of the sector's current performance across the 20 resilience factors, and thus in the 5 broader resilience dimensions, was conducted among stakeholders and experts to provide values for the formula (Dm_i).

For more detailed information on the development of the composite index, the previous work carried out by the REDE research group in the context of a Galician port can be consulted².

RI results and proposals for adaptation

Figure 3. Final results of the Resilience Index for the mussel aquaculture in Galicia (Spain).

Figure 3 visually represents the values obtained for the big five dimensions. However, as mentioned, those dimensions were divided in four resilience factors each, making a total of 20 resilience factors that were also assessed. Every resilience factor represents a line of action. Therefore, the results of the RI allowed to pinpoint the lines of action that contribute in a high level to the value chain resilience and, at the same time, present a higher margin for improvement.

The result of this analysis was the identification of **six priority lines of action** out of twenty, related to (1) making operational procedures more flexible, (2) opening new communication channels, (3) incorporating innovative techniques in production, (4) integrating aquaculture in the context of the wider ecosystem in which it is developed, (5) improving models for predicting changes in oceanic-

² León-Mateos, F., Sartal, A., López-Manuel, L., & Quintas, M. A. (2021). Adapting our sea ports to the challenges of climate change: Development and validation of a Port Resilience Index. *Marine Policy*, 130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2021.104573>

meteorological variables and (6) designing contingency plans for emergencies caused by the effects of climate change.

Beyond the numbers: A strategic roadmap on adaptation actions

As mentioned earlier, the RI aims to **assist decision-makers** in the productive and political fields in making informed decisions about governance and policy formulation to adapt to climate change. The final phase of the RI involved **guiding stakeholders** to define specific actions based on the RI result

Using insights from literature reviews and sector feedback, 24 specific adaptation actions were proposed, aligned with the 6 priority lines identified by the RI. These actions were prioritized during a workshop with stakeholders and experts on May 24, 2024, to draft a strategic roadmap for mussel aquaculture. This ensured the RI's practical applicability by those it was designed to assist.

Figure 4. From left to right, Andrea Ogando (UVigo-REDE) presenting the results of the RI, and stakeholders/ experts participating in the prioritization of solutions. Workshop held on 24th of May 2024.

As a result of this workshop, the following areas for improvement were highlighted:

- Emphasis on enhancing **systematic, long-term ocean-meteorological and environmental data** collection with affordable, easy-to-implement sensors.
- Development and adoption of **predictive analytical tools** for future event anticipation.
- Improvement of **information flows** along the supply chain.
- Promotion of **innovation** through new technologies and collaborative projects.

This collaborative dialogue established an initial framework for action, providing a reference for future programs that integrate current **scientific advances and long-term consultation processes**. The outcomes offer a starting point for defining a common roadmap to enhance the sector's resilience, guiding necessary future actions. By functioning like a health check of the sector's adaptive capacity, the RI pinpoint where is needed to **focus efforts** and **resources** to significantly increase the sector resilience.

Conclusions

The development of the Operational Resilience Index (RI) for the mussel aquaculture sector underscores the importance of **inclusive stakeholder and expert engagement**, using the Quintuple Helix framework to ensure scientific rigor and practical relevance integrating diverse perspectives to address climate change challenges comprehensively. The collaborative approach produced a resilient, adaptive framework and actionable strategies for the sector's sustainability with two main outcomes:

- **Strategic Guidance:** The RI provided actionable recommendations for adaptation, fostering collaboration among stakeholders and supporting informed decision-making.
- **Clear Insights:** The complex data were translated into clear, practical insights, making them accessible to a broader audience and empowering stakeholders to proactively enhance the sector's resilience to climate challenges.

By integrating diverse perspectives and expertise, the development of the Resilience Index exemplified a participatory approach that ensured the tool was tailored to the specific needs and challenges of the mussel aquaculture sector, thereby enhancing its overall impact and effectiveness.

Further information

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1.2 Coastal contracts Sardinia, Italy

Fostering cross-sectoral cooperation for integrated wetland management

A Coastal Contract is a governance approach that facilitates better, cross-sectoral cooperation at the local level. The Coastal Contract is designed for the integrated management of coastal wetlands while overcoming the fragmentation of local governance.

Key learnings

- Collaboration among **different levels of governance** (local and regional scale) and between public and private sectors towards the integrated management of the Gulf of Oristano
- Engagement of **local communities** raises awareness on the importance of wetlands as natural water retention areas in case of climatic events
- Monitor wetland status by a Local Wetland Observatory (LWO) to support **decision-making**
- **Funding:** Better cooperation and planning enabled a more coordinated search for funding

About the region

The coastal region of Oristano in Sardinia, Italy, comprises a complex system of rivers, lagoons, and salt marshes with high environmental value. Most of these wetlands are protected under the Ramsar Convention and the Natura 2000 network and are leased to local fishermen's cooperatives.

Climate and oceanographic hazards

Sea level rise, storms, high temperature, flooding, drought, extreme precipitations

Sector: Integrated water management

Key system: Wetlands

Climate Threats

The Gulf of Oristano, in the western coast of Sardinia, is particularly susceptible to marine storms and torrential rains, posing a substantial risk of inland **flooding**. Another risk are the scorching summers with prolonged **heatwaves**, unpredictable droughts punctuated by intense rainfall. This not only threatens the safety and well-being of the local population but also jeopardizes vital economic pillars like agriculture, fishing, and aquaculture. However, this scenario also presents an opportunity to rethink resilience and innovation.

Revitalizing Wetlands: A New Era of Collaborative Environmental Governance

Healthy wetlands are crucial in mitigating global warming, acting as natural carbon sinks and providing resilience against extreme climatic events. The management of wetlands however is typically challenged by the fragmentation of governmental responsibilities. Governance mechanisms that encourage **multi-actor cooperation** are considered as a good practice in river basin management. The River Basin Management Plans under the **Water framework Directive** are examples of cooperative action at the (larger) river basin scale. At the local scale, e.g. a smaller river, bay or wetland, less examples exist of collaborative integrated management. In Belgium, France and Italy, the concept of river contracts is used to facilitate multi-actor cooperation at smaller rivers. In the Gulf of Oristano a Coastal Contract had been formulated in an **intense stakeholder involvement** process involving economic actors, civil society, and public administration with the objective to **facilitate cooperation and joint management** of the coastal wetlands and the bay of Oristano. The Coastal Contract has been endorsed by local municipalities, together with regional and provincial authorities.

The Coastal Contract represents a voluntary and inclusive agreement among various partners who recognize the territory of the Gulf of Oristano as part of a unique ecosystem and want to actively collaborate towards its protection and commit themselves to base their activities on a broad stakeholder involvement. Driven by this **shared commitment** and supported by a constructive **dialogue**, participants had the opportunity to bring their experiences and proposals, highlighting both individual territorial characteristics and common needs. This process has been crucial in shaping an ambitious and effective Action Plan.

Figure 5. Meeting of the Coastal Contract Coordination Group. Photo credit: MEDSEA Foundation

“We have extremely important wetlands which represent key habitat in the Mediterranean region and if we continue to act individually, we won’t get the result that we are all hoping for.”

Sandro Pili, Mayor of Terralba, Italy

This initiative has led to significant advancements:

Innovative Collaborative Governance: The Coastal Contract serves as a blueprint for how multi-level collaboration can drive both economic growth and environmental sustainability, bridging the gap between local needs and regional strategies.

Enhanced Engagement and Awareness: The community recognised that wetlands are both part of their cultural identity but also a nature-based solution for climate resilience.

Evidence-based making: the Local Wetland Observatory, a hub for data and research, ensures that every action taken is grounded in science and aligned with the needs of the ecosystems and communities.

Figure 6. Photos of the participatory meetings aimed at public and private stakeholders from the municipalities involved in the Coastal Contract, organized between June and July 2023- Photo credit: Poliste srl – Società Benefit

“The contract helps to promote good practices. All fishermen must work harder to guarantee a sustainable fishery and create a model that is applicable to all Mediterranean lagoons.”

Alessandro Porcu, director of Sant’Andrea Fishermen Cooperative. S’Ena Arrubia Pond, Arborea.

The Transformative Journey of the TransformAr Project

Within the framework of the TransformAr Project, partners are working to enhance the use of the Coastal Contract for the protection of water bodies in the Gulf of Oristano and encourage its replicability across Sardinia. Thanks to a consolidated participatory process and the development of the Local Wetland Observatory, the project is reaching a broader involvement of public authorities, local communities, fishermen, farmers, and tourism operators, and guaranteeing a scientific approach in the development of wetland conservation and adaptation measures. The Observatory facilitates informed, evidence-based decisions and raises public awareness about the crucial role of wetlands in climate protection.

The acquisition of new funding for the Action Plan's implementation, coupled with the growing engagement of local stakeholders in public meetings on wetlands, and the surge in proposals for various actions and initiatives, collectively highlight the effectiveness of this governance tool.

Figure 7. Aerial view of the coastal wetland system in the Gulf of Oristano, Sardinia (Italy). Photo credit: Egidio Trainito

THE NUMBERS OF THE COASTAL CONTRACT

14 Signatories (including municipalities, local and regional authorities)

4 governance bodies:

1) Coordination group; 2) Technical secretariat; 3) Committee for directions; 4) Technical committee

50 Actions affecting the integrated system or a specific site;

7 Strategic Axes in which the actions are grouped:

- Governance and capacity building
- Improvement of the ecological status of water systems
- Protection of biodiversity and natural capital
- Landscape development and promotion of cultural heritage
- Green Economy
- Enhancement of the resilience to climate change
- Communication and environmental education

50% of the Actions funded and starting the implementation phase;

50% requesting new funds for the implementation in the medium term;

Summary

The efforts for the development and implementation of the Coastal Contract in the Gulf of Oristano, demonstrate a commitment to integrated, multi-level and participatory governance of wetlands by all stakeholders involved. This approach is reshaping the management of wetlands, focusing on their role in mitigating climate change impacts and promoting a green economy. The progress of this initiative sets a model for sustainable conservation and effective governance, inspiring other regions to adopt similar practices for a resilient Europe.

Further information

<https://www.medseafoundation.org/index.php/en/portfolio-ita-2/transformar/49>

<https://www.medseafoundation.org/index.php/en/portfolio-ita-2/coastal-contract/69>

<https://transformar.eu/demonstrator-4-oristano-italy/>

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1.3 Climate innovation hub in Egaleo, Greece

Climate resilience and socially sustainable development

In municipality of Egaleo an ecosystem of solutions targeting the climate impacts on the health sector, infrastructures and urban planning, is being implemented to enhance just climate resilience and sustainable development while addressing the impacts of climate change.

Key learnings

- **Collaboration** between public, private, and civil society organizations aiming to enhance the strategic planning for addressing the impacts of climate change.
- Engagement of citizens raises climate **awareness** and tries to clear misconceptions about what climate change is, what the impacts are, how it can be tackled, etc.
- Acquisition of **expertise** in innovative and sustainable solutions related to urban planning.

About the region

Egaleo, Greece, is situated at the west region of the urban planning complex of the region of Attica and has been built at both sides of the ancient road «Iera Odos». It is approximately 4km away from Athens.

Climate hazards

Heat waves, extreme precipitations, thunderstorms, and flooding events.

Key system

Health, infrastructures, and urban planning

Solutions

Smart Climate Stations, Citizen App, Awareness-raising, Climate Innovation Hub, Social services/infrastructures

Figure 8. Administrative boarder of Egaleo

Climate vulnerability, impacts and challenges

The municipality of Egaleo, being part of the Western Region of Attica in Greece, belongs to the wider Mediterranean biogeographical region. As thoroughly assessed by Copernicus Climate data, Egaleo is at high risk of **drought**, increased temperatures, decreasing precipitation and **wildfires** in the Egaleo Grove. **Heatwaves** pose a serious threat of heat stress to elderly citizens, vulnerable groups, and households that cannot afford adequate heating and cooling, highlighting the issue of increased energy poverty. Among the major natural risks threatening Egaleo are fires caused by severe temperatures and the dryness of vegetation during the summer months. Although Egaleo has not experienced a direct wildfire event in the Baroutadiko Grove, each summer the temperatures have reached up to 45°C, putting the municipality in a state of heightened alert.

Another significant natural risk for Egaleo is **flooding** caused by urban flash floods, due to insufficient flood risk management systems. Egaleo is located near the Kifissos River, which poses a high risk of flooding during mid-autumn and winter, causing significant damage to the area. Severe floods that resulted in fatalities occurred in 1934, 1954, and 1997.

All these risks are amplified by the city's outdated urban planning, insufficient national funding and the large presence of vulnerable social groups in the city, expanding the impact of severe climate effects in human health with unprepared civic support services.

The issues that Egaleo is facing also increase the area's mainly social vulnerabilities to climate change, such as:

- Slow population growth, high unemployment rates, and the prevalence of vulnerable groups (e.g., migrants, socially disadvantaged individuals). These groups often lack the resources to protect themselves against severe climate impacts, and Egaleo's slower economic growth makes it difficult to support them adequately.
- Infrastructural challenges, particularly inefficient street planning, a lack of public spaces, and insufficient parking facilities. This leads to overcrowded public areas and increased traffic, which can exacerbate environmental harm in the area.
- Direct environmental issues caused by industrial activities in the Eleonas and Yula areas.
- Rising temperatures in Egaleo during the summer months serve as evidence of the reality and impact of climate change. This could encourage citizens to become more aware of their living habits and adopt an eco-friendlier lifestyle (e.g., using public transportation more frequently, reducing household electricity usage, and avoiding littering).

Description of the solutions in TransformAr

There are three Key Community Systems (KCS) in which Egaleo implements solutions to mitigate the impacts of climate change include **health**, **infrastructure**, and **urban planning**. Within the framework of the TransformAr project, Egaleo develops a series of integrated solutions aimed at fostering climate **awareness** and enhancing the **capacity** of both the **municipality** and its **citizens** to **adapt** to climate change. These solutions will involve the collection and analysis of data from various sources, followed by the post-processing of this **data**. The resulting insights will be used to raise public awareness of climate issues and to inform **evidence-based policy** recommendations for climate adaptation at the local level. The solutions being implemented are as follows:

1. Smart climate stations (SCS)

Egaleo is focused on the installation of 21 Smart Climate Stations (SCS) across key locations within the city. The primary objective of these stations is to collect real-time data on the city's

microclimate, enabling the public administration to better prepare citizens for potential climate emergencies. Following careful analysis and planning, the key locations have been identified, and the stations will commence operation during this demonstration. The stations will monitor various parameters, including temperature, relative humidity, atmospheric pressure, CO₂ levels (ppm), PM 2.5/10 (ppm), wind speed, and rainfall.

2. Citizen app engagement (CAE)

Egaleo develops a mobile application designed for both data collection and information dissemination. The app will serve three main functions: (1) it will be used to crowdsource data on the climate awareness of the Egaleo's citizens through questionnaires, (2) it will disseminate information about the TransformAr project's solutions implemented in the municipality, and (3) it will provide notifications regarding climate-related events.

3. Awareness-raising modules (AWAR)

Egaleo develops and tests a curriculum of 45 min for pupils between 13-15 years old related to climate change understanding and climate awareness. Beyond this, a living lab is being created with the participation of the community, within the framework of which stakeholders design actions to address the impacts of climate change.

4. Climate innovation hub (CIH)

Egaleo transforms a multi-purpose facility into a Climate Innovation Hub by: (a) establishing a permanent exhibition on climate change and the TransformAr solutions implemented by the municipality, (b) showcasing real-time data streaming from Smart City Systems (SCS) along with the post-processed indicators, and (c) organizing a series of events aimed at promoting climate innovation (e.g., datathons). These initiatives will provide public access to the municipality's data and encourage the development of innovative solutions to address the municipality's climate-related challenges.

5. Demand analysis for social services/infrastructures (DSI)

Egaleo offers a range of social and health services to its citizens. Due to the impacts of climate change, the demand for these services is expected to shift. In preparation for maintaining uninterrupted service provision and addressing future demand, a comprehensive demand analysis of social services and infrastructure will be conducted. This analysis will generate data to inform the development of an adaptation strategy, considering the future supply and demand of social services.

Figure 9 illustrates the coupling of the solutions and the flow of information from data sources to communication channels.

Figure 9. Illustration of the solution working complementarily to each other. Smart climate stations (SCS), Demand analysis for social services/infrastructures (DSI), Citizen app engagement (CAE), Awareness-raising modules (AWAR), Climate innovation hub (CIH)

The element of innovation in TransformAr- The impacts

Within the framework of the TransformAr Project, the innovations of the Egaleo’s solutions can be categorized into three main areas: (a) the streaming dataset, which is composed of various types, formats, and resolutions (CAE, SCS, DSI, post-processed data), offering a unique resource for a municipality; (b) the integration and utilization of this data for evidence-based policy recommendations, coupled with raising awareness at the citizen level (CAE, AWAR) and promoting innovation (CIH); and (c) the replicability and transferability of the municipality’s ecosystem of solutions, as the core concept (Data, Analysis, Action) can be adapted with different components while maintaining the same overarching objectives.

The impacts of each solution are outlined in Table 2. These impacts are categorized as either direct, meaning they result directly from the implementation of the solution, or indirect, meaning they contribute to the effects of other solutions or to long-term actions that extend beyond the duration and scope of the TransformAr project.

Table 2 Description of the expected impacts per solution

Solution	Expected impact
Smart climate stations (SCS)	<p>(a) The collected data provide a comprehensive dataset on weather and environmental conditions. This information will be visualized through the Citizen Application Engagement (CAE) solution and partially disseminated to the residents to promote climate awareness at the municipal level.</p> <p>(b) The data utilized by the National Center for Scientific Research "Demokritos" (NCSR), a technical partner of the Egaleo, to support the organization's climate and environmental research. In turn, NCSR provides the municipality with a localized, high-resolution weather forecast for the next 120 hours. This forecast will be directly employed as an early warning system to notify relevant municipal departments (e.g., Civil</p>

	<p>Protection, Municipal Police) and other first responders of abnormal temperature or precipitation levels, helping to prevent casualties and disruptions to municipal social services.</p> <p>(c) Beyond the TransformAr initiative, the data collected through the Smart Climate Solutions (SCS) will be used to monitor the effectiveness of various actions and measures implemented in Egaleo. By comparing measurements and relevant indicators before and after implementation, this data will facilitate the quantification and formulation of evidence-based policy recommendations.</p>
Demand analysis for social services/infrastructures (DSI)	<p>Accurately forecasting shifts in the demand for social services as a result of climate change will allow Egaleo to effectively plan for the sustained provision of these services. This includes meeting evolving demands and adapting to new climate conditions and extreme events, such as increasingly intense and frequent heatwaves. For example, special accommodation areas for vulnerable groups are to be set up during heatwaves.</p>
Citizen app engagement (CAE)	<p>As the CAE platform establishes a two-way communication channel between the municipality and the public, it is anticipated to influence not only public understanding of climate change but also to offer to the municipality a means to monitor the impact of other TransformAr solutions. This can be achieved either directly, through questionnaires that specifically reference these solutions, or indirectly, by quantifying overall climate awareness.</p>
Awareness-raising modules (AWAR)	<p>AWAR is expected to enhance young people's understanding of climate change and address common misconceptions about its nature, impacts, and potential solutions. By doing so, it aims to foster a more climate-aware generation that actively pursues mitigation and adaptation efforts at both the municipal level and through broader social transformation. Additionally, through the community's involvement in decision-making processes for addressing the phenomenon of climate change, citizens will become more aware of actions to combat the issue, collaborate with and trust municipal services, and take a more active role in the municipality's initiatives.</p>
Climate innovation hub (CIH)	<p>The CIH comprises two key components: (i) a static climate exhibition designed to present Egaleo's climate actions to the public, and (ii) a dynamic section featuring live streaming and visualization of various datasets collected and processed by the Egaleo. Both components aim to raise climate awareness among exhibition visitors. Additionally, making these datasets available to SMEs, groups, and teams through events such as datathons or Open Green Day is expected to promote innovation and generate solutions for current and future climate-related challenges faced by the Egaleo.</p>

Transformative action plan and combination of solutions

Within the framework of the living lab workshops, two meetings were held. In the first workshop, *“Development of a shared vision and socio-economic pathways of a climate resilient future”* participants created pathways leading to the management of climate change.

Figure 10. Photo from the *“Development of a shared vision and socio-economic pathways of a climate resilient future”* workshop. 10.10.2022

In the second workshop, *“Adaptation action plan development workshop”* the most effective pathways were selected, and actions were designed to achieve this purpose. Building upon these pathways, stakeholders, during the *“Adaptation action plan development workshop”*, crafted an action plan targeting three Key Community Systems (KCS): health, infrastructure, and urban planning. The workshop included members from different Municipal Departments (civil protection, social services, police), political representatives from the municipal council, local schools, researchers, and other local representatives.

The primary concern expressed by nearly all participating stakeholders was the practical implementation of the pathways, including questions regarding financial security, the assurance of collaboration among relevant Municipal Departments, and the mechanisms for effective monitoring and execution in Egaleo. In response, the team from Egaleo and NCSR D elaborated on the foundational support provided by TransformAr and outlined how other Departments would contribute to the successful implementation of the pathways.

“Patios and open spaces in schools must be covered with materials that reduce the temperatures”.

Andreas Rigatos, Principal of the 3rd Middle High School of Egaleo, Greece

Figure 11. Photos from the Adaptation action plan development workshop. 9.7.2024

"An advantage of the city is the fact that the grove is located at the center of Egaleo"
 Konstantinos Samios, Municipal counselor, Egaleo, Greece

TransformAr: A youth regeneration project

As part of the actions implemented at the Climate Innovation Hub, the Open Green Day was organized. The event was highly successful, and in addition to presenting the program's key initiatives, local school students participated by showcasing their own environmental projects. Moreover, a hackathon on climate change was organized, in which the children participated with great enthusiasm. The outcome of these activities, along with the implementation of educational programs, strengthens the environmental awareness of the children and creates a generation that is ready and mature to face the impacts of climate change.

Figure 12. Photos from the Open Green Day, 4.6.2024

Summary

In Egaleo, efforts are focused on enhancing climate resilience and sustainable development through a series of integrated solutions targeting key sectors such as health, infrastructure, and urban planning. Egaleo faces significant risks from climate change, including droughts, wildfires, and urban flash floods, which threaten the area's population and infrastructure. The TransformAr project supports the implementation of innovative solutions like Smart Climate Stations, mobile apps, and educational programs to increase climate awareness and readiness. Community engagement, such as the Open Green Day and climate hackathons, strengthens environmental consciousness among citizens, particularly the younger generation, preparing them to address climate challenges.

Further information

<https://www.aigaleo.gr/>

<https://smartcity.Egaleo.gr/>

<https://inrastes.demokritos.gr/el/areas/energeia-asfaleia-kai-perivallontikes-technologies/>

<https://transformar.eu/demonstrator-6-city-of-Egaleo-greece/>

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Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories.

Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed by means of 9 Transformational Adaptive Blocks. A set of 22 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions.

TransformAr

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon H2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement 101036683.

